

Generating CGRA Processing Element Hardware with CGRAgen

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Abstract—The popularity of the Internet of Things and next-generation wireless networks calls for a greater distribution of small but high-performance and energy-efficient compute devices at the networks’ Edge. These devices must integrate hardware acceleration to meet the latency requirements of relevant use cases. Existing work has highlighted Coarse-Grained Reconfigurable Arrays (CGRAs) as suitable compute architectures for this purpose. However, like other modern hardware design, research and design space exploration into CGRAs is hindered by long development times needed for Register Transfer Level implementation. In this paper, we propose mitigating these by extending the open-source CGRAgen tool with a Chisel-based hardware backend capable of transforming abstract Processing Element (PE) descriptions into synthesizable Verilog code. We present how CGRAgen’s internal module representation is transformed to Chisel modules and demonstrate this on a selection of PE architectures from the literature. Finally, we outline future work on extending this flow to generate entire CGRAs.

Index Terms—chisel, coarse-grained reconfigurable array, computational offloading, hardware generators

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing popularity of the Internet of Things (IoT) follows growing numbers of devices to serve and amounts of data that need processing [1]. Avoiding overwhelming the network backhaul with these factors implies a need for distributed processing [2]. Yet, as end devices are resource-constrained, they often need to offload compute-heavy tasks to more powerful devices; traditionally, in the Cloud [3]. Recently, however, the Edge computing paradigm has gained popularity as it permits end devices to retain the benefits of offloading while mitigating the latency and energy consumption drawbacks of Cloud computing [3], [4].

Edge computing is enabled by devices that have become more powerful and by applications, such as Machine Learning, being inherently tolerant to constrained computational errors as they aggregate noisy data into new information [3], [5]. Still, Edge devices remain constrained in size and battery capacity, forcing them to integrate reconfigurable hardware accelerators to attain satisfactory performance and energy efficiency [6]. Coarse-Grained Reconfigurable Arrays (CGRAs) are interesting in this regard as they: 1) are generic enough to support a wide range of applications, 2) balance reconfigurability well with its associated overheads [7], and 3) may

implement hardware-level Approximate Computing (AxC) to save more energy when error tolerances permit [5]. Though some CGRAs may operate as standalone processing systems, we consider them co-processors to the Edge device’s CPU used to improve performance and energy efficiency.

Common CGRA architectures comprise arrays of possibly heterogeneous Processing Elements (PEs) interconnected by a potentially configurable fabric or network [6], [7]. As such, designing a CGRA is non-trivial, and existing designs are primarily described in traditional Register Transfer Level (RTL) using VHDL or (System)Verilog [8], [9]. Yet, identifying the proper balance between hardware costs and reconfigurability – including that required for integrating AxC techniques [5] – involves a time-consuming, and often costly, design space exploration. Reducing these costs is highly desirable. For this reason, some existing work proposes templated RTL that permits customization before synthesis [10]–[12], while others rely on in-house, hand-written (System)Verilog generators [13]–[15]. However, such implementations are error-prone and may severely limit the possible extent of one’s exploration.

Recent work has instead turned to embedded HDLs for greater flexibility: OpenCGRA [16] uses PyMTL (Mamba) embedded in Python [17], while Pillars [18] uses Chisel embedded in Scala [19]. Unfortunately, OpenCGRA relies heavily on a pre-defined PE architecture template, while Pillars suffers from two issues: firstly, it remains reliant on an outdated version of Chisel; and second, its Scala-based ADL is involved and has some redundancy. Motivated by these deficiencies, we instead focus on the generic, parameterized architecture modeling flow of CGRAgen [6], which is based on a simple ADL, but lacks a hardware generation backend. We propose a flow combining CGRAgen’s modeling capabilities with the software-defined hardware construction functionalities of Chisel [19]. In this paper, we cover the first steps in this direction, presenting our work on extending CGRAgen to output hardware descriptions for generic PEs described in its simple ADL. Our main contribution is this extension, which is to be part of a comprehensive hardware backend for CGRAgen to generate entire CGRAs and associated control hardware.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II briefly introduces CGRAs, the Chisel framework, and the CGRAgen flow. Next, Section III presents our work on extending CGRAgen to generate generic PE hardware architectures, including a design space exploration on configuration hardware, before Section IV demonstrates this functionality with some popular,

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Fig. 2: High-level overview of CGRAgen. The tool takes two inputs: a CGRA description in its *CGRA-ADL* [6, Lst. 1] and a DFG in the .dot format [27]. This paper considers only the blue elements. Dashed elements outline future work.

The flexibility of CGRAgen’s architecture modeling module represents a major motivation for working with it. Its ADL is simple, yet it supports declaring constants (denoted by definition), hierarchical module templates, and mesh-style architectures of module instances in various patterns. A collection of predefined primitives, including ALUs, registers, multiplexers, and IO blocks, serve as the basis for all modules. A designer can specify the desired bit width of all these as well as, for example, the types of operations supported by an ALU and their respective latencies and initiation intervals. For simplicity, the tool comes with default values for all these parameters. connections between instances of primitives or templated modules are either one-to-one (using the `from` and `to` attributes), many-to-one (using `select-from` and `to`), or one-to-many (using `from` and `distribute-to`). An example PE template description is shown in Fig. 3, while the full ADL is specified in [6, Lst. 1].

III. GENERATING PROCESSING ELEMENT HARDWARE WITH CGRAgen

Our extension is modeled closely after CGRAgen’s existing architecture modeling capabilities, maintaining the same distinction between primitives and composite modules, and makes full use of Chisel’s dynamic hardware generation capabilities. Before diving into hardware generation, it is worth noting that within CGRAgen, hardware modules are modeled as instances of the `AbstractModule` class or inheriting classes thereof, which include information about module ports, sub-modules, and connections between these. The aforementioned primitives all inherit from this class but have manually described functionality. Sub-modules of composite modules may be either primitives or other composite modules generated during architecture parsing. All primitive modules that involve control signals maintain information about these internally.

A. Hardware Generation Flow

While CGRAgen’s architecture modeling flow makes wide use of companion objects to simplify its Application Programming Interface (API), Chisel’s context requirements prevent such an approach. Instead, we implement a hierarchy of classes extending Chisel’s `Module` class and parameterize them by a CGRAgen `AbstractModule` or one of its inheriting classes, as illustrated in Fig. 4. Composite modules are generated according to the following steps:

- 1) Name the module using Chisel’s `desiredName` API.
- 2) Recursively create all sub-modules and add them to the current module.
- 3) Create all data ports and add them to the current module.
- 4) Connect current module and sub-module ports.
- 5) Construct configuration hardware:
 - If the current module is the top-level, implement parallel or serial configuration hardware;
 - otherwise, pass through sub-module control ports.

Primitives are described in each their own class, which implements their respective parameterized logic. By nature, their logic tends to be rather simple and would, under normal design circumstances, likely be inlined within larger composite modules. Nevertheless, our flow maintains these separately to exploit the code-sharing benefits of inheritance.

Like the existing parts of CGRAgen, our extension assumes that the PEs in a CGRA operate in lockstep. However, despite supporting parameterized ALUs with different operation initiation intervals and latencies for mapping and scheduling [6], our extension is, so far, limited to operations with initiation intervals of 1 cycle, i.e., ones that may be issued every cycle. Supporting operations with other initiation intervals would require ALUs to implement some kind of hand-shaking, whose control signals CGRAgen cannot yet produce.

It is important to note that the architectural modeling flow of CGRAgen provides two more primitives than our hardware generation flow: `AbstractInputUnits` and `AbstractOutputUnits` [6]. The mapping flow needs these for modeling data input and output operations, while they merely represent simple top-level ports in hardware. Our flow, therefore, converts these primitives to data ports of their containing module (in step 3 listed above) and provides pass-through connections to the top module’s IO, if necessary. However, as CGRAgen supports hierarchical modules, such primitives can in principle be sub-modules at any level. This poses a challenge to the usual hardware generation flow in Chisel – that modules are fully specified within their constructors – as a module’s IO now potentially depends on the IO of its sub-modules. Moreover, it partially impedes the benefits of inheritance as a parent class’ constructor is called before the child class’ constructor in Scala.

We resolve this issue by taking two simple steps. Firstly, we let each module keep track of data inputs and outputs in

(a) PE block diagram.

```
<template name="simplePE">
  <input name="I0"/> <input name="I1"/>
  <output name="O0"/> <output name="O1"/>
  <inst name="res" module="Register"/>
  <inst name="alu" module="FuncUnit" ops="add sub"/>
  <connection from="alu.out" to="res.in"/>
  <connection select-from="this.I0 this.I1 res.out" to="alu.in_a"/>
  <connection select-from="this.I0 this.I1 res.out" to="alu.in_b"/>
  <connection from="res.out" distribute-to="this.O0 this.O1"/>
</template>
```

(b) Abstract ADL description.

```
module simplePE(
  input clock,
  input reset,
  input [31:0] io_ins_I1,
  input [31:0] io_ins_I0,
  output [31:0] io_outs_O1,
  output [31:0] io_outs_O0,
  input [7:0] ctrl_ins_conf,
  input ctrl_ins_conf_en;
  ...
endmodule
```

(c) Verilog module description.

Fig. 3: Illustrated design flow from block diagram through ADL description to Verilog code using CGRAgen. Colored elements are related. The Verilog description is truncated, leaving out instantiation and interconnect of all sub-modules.

two mutable.HashMap[String, UInt]-type fields defined in the Buildable class, see Fig. 4. These maps are converted into Chisel Records before being included in the module’s IO value, which we mark as lazy to ensure that it is not elaborated during construction, but only once referenced. This strategy for defining modules with dynamic IO is enabled by Chisel being embedded in Scala and has, to the best of our knowledge, not been applied outside of RocketChip’s *Diplomacy* package before [28]. The resulting definition is shown in Listing 1.

```
protected val _inputs =
  mutable.HashMap.empty[String, UInt]
protected val _outputs =
  mutable.HashMap.empty[String, UInt]

lazy val io = IO(new Bundle {
  val ins = Input(
    new PortRecord[UInt](_inputs.toMap))
  val outs = Output(
    new PortRecord[UInt](_outputs.toMap))
})
```

Listing 1: Declaration of the Buildable class’ lazy IO value.

Secondly, we integrate the above hardware generation flow in two methods: build() and buildConfig(), which are responsible for points 2 through 4 and the remaining points listed

Fig. 4: Hierarchy of public (green) and private (purple) classes of our hardware generation package, hwgen.

above, respectively. The methods are automatically called within the constructor of the Buildable class, meaning that also inheriting classes will have them called in the same order. We exploit this feature and override the build() method in the PrimitiveUnit class to more easily implement the manual functionality of the primitives. Both methods carefully add all ports before referencing their related IO fields.

To the best of our knowledge, no traditional HDL supports dynamic IO declarations, hence, the benefits of using Chisel for our use case are clear. Nonetheless, we discovered one slight downside: namely that when referencing an unelaborated port for the first time, Chisel’s naming plugin may alter its name depending on the assignment it is used in. This behavior is crucial to ensure that module-internal signals are uniquely named, and one may consider it negligible when it affects sub-module ports; yet, a designer would expect the top-level module’s IO to match their ADL description. Moreover, port name uniqueness is already guaranteed by CGRAgen’s architecture modeling flow. Thus, to counter these effects, we have utilized the suggestName() and noPrefix{} annotations in all signal assignment statements.

B. Configuration Hardware

As mentioned above, primitives that require control signals keep track of such internally. For mapping purposes, each control signal is assigned a so-called configuration cell; in hardware, a simple register. Within our hardware generation flow, these configuration cells are collected within the top-level module and their outputs are passed through the sub-module hierarchy to drive their associated ports. For all modules, these ports are modeled identically to the data IO, though named ctrl instead of io.

The configuration hardware generation is managed by an enumerated type parameter to the Buildable class, which affects the behavior of the buildConfig() method. In the current implementation, we distinguish between three styles of configuration:

- NoConfiguration All modules that are not the top-level one are marked by this type. Consequently, they simply

implement the aforementioned pass-through connections of sub-module control ports.

- **ParallelConfiguration** A top-level module marked by this type will implement a wide register all of whose bits can be over-written in one cycle. The resulting top-level `ctrl` ports include a configuration input, `conf_in`, and an enable signal for the register, `conf_en`.
- **SerialConfiguration** A top-level module marked by this type will implement a wide shift register whose configuration bits are shifted in one at a time. The resulting top-level `ctrl` ports include a scan input, `scan_in`, a scan enable, `scan_en`, and a scan output, `scan_out`.

For both parallel and serial configuration types, we collect sub-module control ports in a wire of type `PortRecord[PortRecord[UInt]]`, as shown in Listing 2. This allows for connecting all of a sub-module’s control ports with a single assignment. In the current literature, the parallel configuration style appears by far the most popular [9], [10], [14], as it enables rapid switches between multiple contexts to execute complex DFGs. However, for highly area-constrained designs focused on frequent re-execution of DFGs mapped to a single context, the serial configuration style may help to reduce hardware costs related to the addressing and configuration of multiple PEs simultaneously, assuming the application can tolerate the relatively longer configuration latency it entails. Note that while there exist intermediate design points capable of shifting in multiple configuration bits per cycle, we do not consider these here.

```
val confWire = Wire(
  new PortRecord[PortRecord[UInt]](
    _subModules.map { case (name, subMod) =>
      name -> subMod.ctrl.ins.cloneType
    }.toMap
  ))
```

Listing 2: Collection of sub-module control inputs to a common wire in configuration hardware generation.

C. Integration with Existing Toolflow

To enable neat integration with the existing flow of CGRAGEN and implement a similar style of API, we provide a callable top-level object `HWGen`. When called on an `AbstractModule`, the object returns the generated Verilog string, assuming the passed module is the top-level. This operation takes place in the main `CGRAGEN` object when a user passes in the command line flag `-gen-hardware`. That is, given that the architecture description used in Fig. 3 exists in the file `./archs/simple.xml`, one may generate the associated hardware description by executing:

```
> sbt runMain cgragen.CGRAGEN ./archs/simple.xml \
| -gen-hardware
```

The resulting hardware descriptions will be available in a newly generated sub-folder under the `./runs` directory. For simplicity, a file is generated for each module template in the architecture description. By default, the top-level module implements parallel configuration hardware.

IV. DEMONSTRATION

To demonstrate the current state of our PE generation flow, we use it to generate Verilog descriptions for four designs from the literature and compare their hardware costs. Specifically, we consider PEs modeled after ADRES [10], CMA [8], HyCUBE [9], and the more recent RF-CGRA [25]. These four designs are interesting for different reasons: ADRES is foundational for the field of CGRAs [7] and its PE has been a source of inspiration for several subsequent architectures like [14], [29]. HyCUBE and its extension in RF-CGRA enable effective multi-cast and multi-hop single-cycle connections by integrating crossbar-like switches within each PE [9, Fig. 3], potentially affecting achievable clock frequency¹. RF-CGRA extends the HyCUBE PE with chainable input registers to enable more flexible mapping. Finally, CMA’s PEs are simple and register-free but provide massive connectivity to their neighbors [8, Fig. 5]. We illustrate these architectures in Figs. 5a through 5d.

For comparability, all ALUs implement all the currently supported operations purely combinatorially: addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, bit shifts, and common bitwise operators. In addition to the elements shown in Fig. 5, all PEs integrate 16-bit constants included in their configuration cells. Internal to a PE, constants are sign-extended to the full data bit width.

With our flow, we produce Verilog descriptions for all these designs with data bit widths of 16 or 32 bits and with either parallel or serial configuration elements. Due to limitations in CGRAGEN [6], we do not implement predication or external configuration memory in ADRES’s [10] and CMA’s [8] PEs, respectively. Subsequently, the designs are synthesized and implemented using AMD Vivado 2022.2 to target a Zynq UltraScale+ FPGA. The reported resource utilization numbers are collected when the designs are implemented for their maximum clock frequencies. To avoid potential issues with input and output timing and IO limitations of the target device, the inputs and outputs are driven by, respectively, drive shift registers. The costs of these registers are subtracted from the final resource utilization numbers. The results include configuration registers; hence, why CMA’s otherwise purely combinational PE has a non-zero number of registers.

Clearly, these designs represent different design points in terms of frequency and resource utilization. Despite all designs implementing identical ALUs, CMA’s PE achieves significantly higher maximum clock frequency than all of the other architectures. The main reason for this is that the critical paths in ADRES’s, HyCUBE’s, and RF-CGRA’s PEs are dominated by costly operand selection logic. The simplest of the designs, ADRES’s PE, expectedly achieves the lowest resource utilization. Small differences in the number of registers used for the same PE architecture with different configuration styles may arise from logic replication needed

¹The original work implements clock-less repeaters between the PEs and claims feasibility of 11 hops in $1ns$ between nodes $1mm$ apart in a $32nm$ process [9].

Fig. 5: Illustration of various PE architectures from the literature used in our evaluation. Port names indicate connections to neighboring PEs to the North (N), East (E), South (S), or West (S), diagonal neighbors, or to row or column buses.

TABLE I: Resource consumption numbers and maximum clock frequencies for the generated PE architectures from ADRES [10], HyCUBE [9], and RF-CGRA [25], when targeting an AMD Zynq UltraScale+ FPGA.

	Width	PE	# LUTs	# Registers	# DSPs	Max clock [MHz]
Parallel Configuration	16	ADRES	586	113	1	66.67
		CMA	868	33	1	250.0
		HyCUBE	755	159	1	68.97
		RF-CGRA	824	160	1	66.67
Parallel Configuration	32	ADRES	1731	199	3	27.40
		CMA	2208	30	3	166.7
		HyCUBE	2296	286	3	27.03
		RF-CGRA	2207	287	3	27.03
Serial Configuration	16	ADRES	560	113	1	64.52
		CMA	810	30	1	250.0
		HyCUBE	706	160	1	66.67
		RF-CGRA	749	162	1	66.67
Serial Configuration	32	ADRES	1685	194	3	27.78
		CMA	2097	30	3	166.7
		HyCUBE	2165	287	3	27.78
		RF-CGRA	2060	288	3	27.78

to match a specified maximum clock frequency. Generally, parallel configuration hardware consumes more LUTs than its serial counterpart.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented an hardware backend extension of the open-source CGRA modeling and mapping flow, CGRAgen, capable of generating generic PE hardware. Using functionalities from CGRAgen’s architecture modeling component, the Chisel-based extension can convert PE architectures described in its ADL to corresponding Verilog code. This permits design space exploration with little effort, illustrated here by a handful of popular PE architectures designed and converted using CGRAgen. The results of this exploration show the diversity of such architectures in terms of resource utilization and achievable clock frequency, underlining the need for tools for rapid design space exploration.

The proposed extension is at the heart of an envisioned, comprehensive hardware backend for CGRAgen capable of generating entire CGRAs. We expect to gradually approach this goal by first implementing the generation of PE interconnects and later control hardware and buffering, including adding support for operations with parameterizable initiation intervals, as described in Section III. Once well-established, we will introduce support for predication, vectorization, and AxC, inspired by existing work [14], [30]. In parallel to adding these features, we will utilize ChiselTest [31] and ChiselVerify [32] to integrate verification of the generated hardware with golden architectural models in software, as shown in Fig. 2.

Source Access

CGRAgen will be published on the APROPOS GitHub page before the conference: <https://github.com/aproposorg>.

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